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Production, Characterization and Kinetic Studies of Proteases by Screening of Indigenous Biomass

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Abstract

Proteases are vital industrial biocatalysts that form the largest group of enzymes acting as proteinases, peptidases, and amidases. Solid State fermentation (SSF) is recognized as an effective method to produce protease enzyme. The enzyme activity profile was obtained by performing enzyme assay showed that corn cobs gave maximum protease activity i.e., 53.297U/mL after seven days of incubation. Response surface methodology (RSM) was used to study the effect of different parameters on enzyme production. From the results inferred by RSM, the maximum enzyme activity was observed at 50°C, at pH 8.0 inoculated with 2mL inoculum size after seven days of incubation. K_M and V_{max} kinetic parameters were calculated 0.5219 mM and 12.19512 mM/min. The unique properties of protease enzyme such as high specificity, biodegradability and decreased the generation of waste materials makes it important enzyme for biotechnological applications.

Keywords: *Aspergillus niger*; Corn Cobs; Purification; Response Surface Methodology; Solid State Fermentation

1. Introduction:

Animals, plants and microorganisms produce protease enzyme that are useful in breakdown of protein and have an important role in various physiological as well as pathological processes (Kuddus *et al.*, 2021). The protease enzymes obtained from plants are bromelain, keratinases and papain (Sawant *et al.*, 2020). Papain is useful in clotting of milk and protein digesting, obtained from fruit Papaya. Bromerlain effectively control the growth of tumor, obtained from pineapple peels (Chanalia *et al.*, 2020). Keratinases enzyme play role in dehairing which is useful in prevention from sewage system blockage

(Yusuf *et al.*, 2021).

Protease enzymes that are obtained from animals are trypsin, pepsin, chymotrypsin and rennins. Trypsin is found in small intestine and help in food digestion. Chymotrypsin is found in pancreas. Rennins found in stomach of mammals with inactive form. It is also used for curd making with good flavors (Velooralappil *et al.*, 2020). Pepsin has acidic nature present in stomach of all vertebrates and it becomes resistant to degradation due to alkaline conditions and high temperature (Adinarayana *et al.*, 2020). Proteases obtained from microorganisms are found in market

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and have more effective qualities like vast biochemical diversity, easy genetic manipulation and many more which attracts biotechnological users (Mishra *et al.*, 2020).

Microorganisms are significant in production of intra and extra-cellular proteases. Intra-cellular protease enzymes are useful for sporulation and extracellular proteases utilized in different industries (Khan, 2020). The participation of protease enzyme guided them to manufacture the therapeutic agent to prevent from fatal diseases, like AIDS and cancer (Rawlings *et al.*, 2021). Proteolytic enzyme found in the microbe and mammals structure are in small size, structurally spherical and dense (Oberoi *et al.*, 2018). The microbial enzymes are divided into groups depend on the acidic or basic characteristics. (Panda *et al.*, 2019). Alkaline proteases are produced through multiple sources (Prakasham *et al.*, 2018). Acid protease enzymes are strong and energetic. The optimum pH of acid protease enzyme is 3-4 (Machado *et al.*, 2018). Acid protease enzymes are utilized in the clearing of fruit juice and tenderizing the fibril muscle (Zhang *et al.*, 2018).

Solid substrate and submerged fermentation methods are utilized due to the cost effectiveness and production of microbial protease enzyme. The wheat bran which is easily available substrate is found to be favorable for the protease production in solid substrate fermentation process (Hamza, 2017b). Other sources of substrate which are cheap, such as cow dung, agro industrial waste, wheat bran and groundnuts are remarkable to the manufacturing of protease (Verma *et al.*, 2016).

There are different methods to improve the protease enzyme yield for economic application, such as screening of the strains and cloning. Various statistical approaches like response surface methodology have also been utilized to the optimization of various growth conditions and media. Both conventional ultra violet (UV) or chemicals and modern rDNA technology are utilized for the strain improvement of protease enzyme hyperproduction

(Rehman *et al.*, 2017).

Enzymes are utilized in many industries. Due to their higher cost production, low stability and recovery is expensive which reduces the application of enzyme. Technologies in the field of enzyme immobilization offer the probability of wide application for cost effective enzymes (Singhal *et al.*, 2020). This review provides an updated overview of proteases to produce, characterize & purify the protease enzyme from *Aspergillus niger*, screen the high yield producing (substrates) and optimize the protease production for industrial application).

1.1 Mechanism Action of Protease Enzyme:

Proteases occur in the intestinal tissues induce few mechanisms of action to participate in pathogenesis. They are forced to do their duties by performing proteolytic processing to other molecules such as mediators, receptors, thereby making a sum of intracellular signals.

1.2 Receptor Activation:

Receptors are expressed in the gastrointestinal tract. These are present in intestinal epithelial cells, fibroblasts, and infiltrated inflammatory cells, mast cells, neurons, respectively. By the proteolytic breakdown, they are activated for their extracellular N-terminal domain, which discharges a novel N-terminal domain to produce intracellular signals (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2017). Members of the PAR family are (PAR1, 2, 3 and 4) can be triggered by serine, cysteine and metalloproteinases. Activation of protease-activated receptors in the gastrointestinal tract makes an extensive array for pro-inflammatory, proliferate effects and pronociceptive. Protease-activated receptors in the gut, are able to induce a number of physiological functions such as ion exchange, permeability secretion, nociception (Coelho *et al.*, 2018), motility etc.

Figure 1: Mechanism Action of Protease Enzyme

1.3. Processing of Inflammatory Mediators:

Protease enzymes also modify the bioactivity for inflammatory mediators. This is used for cytokines, chemokines and their related receptors. Proteolytic breakdowns increase, when the bioactivity of chemokines and cytokines by stimulating the processing for a quiet precursor, improving their pro-inflammatory properties. For example, CXCL-8 and 5 that is cleaved by proteinase-3 and cathepsin G, the abbreviated forms of these chemokines having higher pro-inflammatory properties for neutrophils (Nufer *et al.*, 2019). Proteinase-3 are utilized to activate interleukin (IL-1 and 18) and tumor necrosis factor

1.1. Objectives:

- To produce and characterize the protease
- To determine the effect of different sources of indigenous biomass on protease kinetic activity.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Microorganism Isolation:

Aspergillus niger strain was used. Fungal strain was used from the lab, University of Gujrat,

Pakistan. PDA media was manufactured for the spore growth as it contains all the ingredients required for growth and development. The mixture in a conical flask was sealed with cotton plug and aluminum foil and sterilized in an autoclave for two hours. In a laminar air flow spores of *A. niger* were transferred in PDA media and kept in the swinging incubator at 33°C at 150rpm for seventy-two hours for the development of fungal spore. The fully grown suspension was stored on 4°C (Sandri *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Agro-based Substrate Inoculation:

Several agro-based waste materials are sugarcane, rice husk, wheat straws and corn cobs were collected locally. All the collected biomass was crushed, washed with water, dried and grinded in to small particles. Five grams of each kind of substrate was taken into 250mL Erlenmeyer flasks. All flasks containing substrates were hydrated with 5mL of water and autoclaved for two hours for the sterilization. All the substrates were inoculated by adding 3mL of fungal spore, and then shifted in the incubator at 35 ±1°C for 4-5 days.

2.3. Enzyme Extraction:

Enzyme was extracted by addition of 50mL distilled water and experimental flasks were taken in

the shaker for 1 hour and filtered through Whatman No.1 filter paper, poured in to the falcon tubes (50mL) for centrifugation at 4400rpm for 30 minutes. After

centrifugation pellet was removed and resultant supernatant was utilized as crude enzyme (Ali *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 2: Enzyme Extraction by Whatman No.1 Filter paper

2.4. Assay of Protease Enzyme:

Protease activity was assayed by the process of Anson in which casein is used as a substrate. 1mL unpurified enzyme and 1mL casein manufactured in 1M phosphate buffer pH range is 7. The mixture was incubated at 35°C for 10 min and reaction was ceased through addition of 2mL Trichloroacetic acid, incubated mixture monitored through centrifugation at 4000 rpm by keeping temperature at 4°C for the 10 min. After centrifugation, 1mL of the supernatant was taken with 5mL of Na₂CO₃ followed by the 1mL of Folin reagent was added to obtain the blue color.

2.5. Optimization of Protease Enzyme:

The experiment was made to investigate the different factors that can affect the protease activity by utilizing response surface methodology. The parameters investigated were inoculum size, temperature, pH, and incubation time for the growth. All factors were crucial for expression of the enzyme.

Trials were performed at varying temperature range (25°C-60°C); and pH ranging from (2.0-10.0) with different inoculum size (1-6) by varying incubation (1-8) days (Ali *et al.*, 2019). Phosphate buffer was utilized at pH range is 8.

2.6. Standard Curve of Protein:

The Lowry method is used in the biochemical assay for determining concentration of the protein in a solution (Sapan & Lunblad, 2015). The principle is that, the copper ion reactivity and nitrogen of peptides in alkaline environment decreases due to folin reagent. Casein standard solution was used as a stock and prepared by dissolving 0.02g protein in 0.1M NaOH. The dilutions in test tubes were prepared ranging from the 0.1-1mL by using stock solution and made final volume up to 1mL through adding distilled water. The absorbance was taken at the 660nm and standard curve for casein was plotted between conc. and its absorbance.

Figure 3: Standard Curve for Protein

2.6.1. Protease Purification:

Ammonium sulphate precipitation technique is used for the purification of proteins. In the ammonium sulphate precipitation salting in and salting out technique was utilized (Yang *et al.*, 2019). One milliliter of the enzyme filtrate was added to the 9 different test tubes while the tenth was treated as blank which contained 1ml distilled water. Place in the freezer overnight. After this procedure, mixture was centrifuged for 20 minutes. Supernatant was kept while the pellet was discarded. Enzyme assay was done at end and the absorbance was taken at the 660nm.

3. Results:

3.1. Influence of PH:

To study the pH impact on enzyme activity, the enzyme activity was quantified through incubating the fermentation process under various pH ranges (2-10). The maximum protease production 53.297U/mL found at pH 8.0 by corn cobs in the (Fig. 1). The result shows that enzyme is alkaline protease. The optimum pH for protease enzyme is comparable to various proteases indicated that optimal pH closer to 8.0 (Seyfzadeh *et al.*, 2017). All detergents used in which enzymes are alkaline in nature have high pH value (Saeki *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 4: Effect of pH on Activity of Protease Enzyme

3.2. Influence of Temperature:

The influence of temperature on the enzyme activity was determined through fermenting at various temperatures ranging from 25°C and 60°C. The

maximum activity of protease enzyme 53.297U/mL obtains at 50°C, also found in the *Bhanerochaete chrusosporium* at 25°C (Morita et al., 2020). It shows that temperature does not affect the rate of growth for organism, also exhibited influence on production of protease enzyme.

Figure 5: Effect of Temperature on Activity of Protease Enzyme

3.3. Influence of Inoculum Size:

All flasks containing 5g substrate was incubated for 3 days at pH 8.0 and temperature 50°C. Solid-state fermentation, corn cobs inoculated with 2ml inoculum size gives maximum enzyme production

(53.297U/mL) in the (Fig. 3). The maximum amount of enzyme was produced when 1.0 mL was added to the flask (Haq et al., 2016). Increase in inoculum size results, the decrease in protease production. Increase in inoculum size causes overcrowding of spores, enzyme activity was decreased (Ahmed et al., 2010).

Figure 6: Effect of Inoculum Size on Activity of Protease Enzyme

3.4. Influence of Incubation Days:

The maximum protease activity is obtained after seventh days of incubation. In the previous

studies, the maximum activity of enzyme was observed after 8 days of fermentation process (Morimura et al., 2018).

Figure 7: Effect of Incubation days on Activity of Protease Enzyme

3.5. Reciprocal Plot for k_M and V_{max} :

The K_M and V_{max} values for enzyme were studied by utilizing casein as a substrate. Results obtained in the form of enzyme activity were used to form reciprocal plot by utilizing Line-Weaver and Burk

equation. The reciprocal of substrate concentration $1/S$ was plotted against reciprocal of enzyme activity $1/V$.

Figure 8: The Lineweaver-Burk plot for Kinetic constants of Protease Enzyme.

4. Discussion:

Biomass screening was the first step for the optimization and production. Total four different substrates were gathered, dried and then crushed in

the appropriate mesh particle size for experiments. The collected biomass was screened to produce the proteases. The enzyme activity was obtained through enzyme assay showed that corn cobs gave maximum protease activity after seven days of incubation.

The influence of temperature for protease production was studied through incubating the media at different temperature ranges; 25, 35, 40, 45 and 50°C. The maximum production of protease enzyme at temperature 50 °C is 53.297U/mL. In the previous studies maximum production of protease enzyme at temperature 40°C gave 4.2 U/ml enzyme activity (Ahmed, 2018).

The optimum temperature of alkaline protease was checked, at different temperatures ranging from 20°C-60°C. Results indicated that protease activity, was increased with the increase in temperature. Further, increase in the temperature beyond this limit resulted decline in enzyme activity. Temperature higher than optimal level causes denaturing of enzyme and fungus growth (Haq et al., 2022).

Higher temperature has an effect on metabolic activities. The Protease enzyme production was observed after 7th days of incubation. In previous studies 8th days of incubation is required for maximum activity (Patil et al., 2018), more days produces mycelium growth.

The protease enzyme production was checked through different pH ranges i.e. 2, 3, 7, 8, 9. The maximum activity of enzyme was observed at pH 8. The maximum activity of enzyme was observed at pH 7.6 from *Bacillus Licheniformis* (Shateri et al., 2021) that is almost similar to our result. P-value for 2-way interaction between pH and incubation days is not significant in the RSM Table which indicates these two factors have not interaction together to enhance the enzyme activity.

The size of inoculum has great influence on the production of protease. An appropriate inoculum size is essential for optimum growth and enzyme production by the microorganism. The maximum amount of enzyme was produced when 2ml of inoculum was added to the fermentation flasks.

By utilizing production medium in which 1% casein are used as the main substrate. The highest activity, which was observed for the protease enzyme production is 3.26 U/ml in 1ml. Inoculum size for the spores suspension in order to verify enzyme activity; spore conc. must be high enough for the colonized substrate particles (Ahmed, 2018).

The size of inoculum was ranged from (0.5ml to 2ml). The maximum amount of enzyme (8.6 U/g) was produced when 1ml of inoculum was added to the fermentation flasks (Maitig et al., 2022). The size of inoculum was different from previous studies. The mycelium was increased; it decreases the substrate concentration for growth and enzyme synthesis (Cavello et al., 2021).

5. Conclusion:

The maximum production i.e. 53.297 U/mL with pH 8.0 and temperature at 50 °C. The unique properties of protease enzyme such as fast action, high specificity, biodegradability and reduced generation of waste materials makes it important for biotechnological applications.

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